

Knowledge Regarding Prevention of Oral Cancer among Adults

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ABSTRACT

Oral cancer is the most common cancer among the adults. The incidence of oral cancer is increasing in India especially in persons with continuous use of tobacco and tobacco products. The present descriptive study was conducted among adults in a selected community Vazhayoor, Malappuram. The objectives of the study were to assess the knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults and to find out the association between socio demographic variables and knowledge. The conceptual frame work of this study was based on Dr. Nola J Pender's Health Promotion Model (HPM). A sample of 100 adults was selected using convenient sampling technique. A non-experimental approach with structured questionnaire was used for this study. The tools used were socio demographic data, questionnaire to find out knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study showed that majority of the subjects (32%) were 31-40 years old, about 38% of samples were males and 62% were females. About 53% of samples have high school education and 21% have degree and above. About 56% of samples were homemakers, 23% have private job. It was found that 33% of subjects have good knowledge on prevention of oral cancer and 64% subjects have average knowledge on prevention of oral cancer. It was revealed that there is no significant association between age, gender, educational status, occupation, type of family, monthly family income and knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults.

Key words: knowledge, prevention, oral cancer, adults of age group 20-60 years.

INTRODUCTION

It has been well recognized since the beginning of this century that oral cancer is one of the commonest cancers in India. For a long time this recognition was based upon hospital frequency statistics by looking at the proportion of oral cancer among all cancer cases diagnosed. The incidence from the National Cancer Registry Project of the Indian Council of Medical Research confirmed the fact that oral cancer was indeed a common form of cancer in India. Over the years, the incidence of oral sub mucous fibrosis in the population has increased manifold - especially among younger generation, possibly leading to a further increase in the incidence of oral cancer. This may be related to the rising trend of pan masala and gutkha chewing in the population. In the developing world, the oral cavity is the fourth commonest site of carcinoma after lung, stomach and liver in males while in females it is the fifth commonest cancer after cervix, breast, stomach and lung. Oral cancer represents 14 % of all cancer cases at Regional Cancer Centre (RCC), Kerala, India. It constituted 17 % of all cancers in males and 10.5 % of all cancers in females making it the commonest cancer in males and the third commonest cancer among females. The spectrum of cancer varies from place to place within our country. Site-specific data from the different parts provide the various trends and give clues to the etiological factors responsible for these significant variations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A quantitative non experimental research approach was chosen for the present study. Research design selected for present study was descriptive design to assess the knowledge regarding the prevention of oral cancer among adults in a selected community Vazhayoor panchayath at Malappuram. Sample size was 100. Non probability convenient sampling was used for the study.

Data were collected by using the following tool.

Tool 1: The data collection technique was structured knowledge questionnaire to assess the knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer.

Section A includes socio-demographic variables of the study participants which include age, gender, religion, education, occupation, type of family, marital status and monthly family income of adults both male and female of age group 20-60 years.

Section B includes structured questionnaire which include 20 questions to assess the knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults both male and female of age group 20-60 years.

Score interpretation

The maximum score for the knowledge questionnaire regarding prevention of oral cancer was 20 and interpretations were as follows:

- Score above 13: Good knowledge.
- Score 7-13 : Average knowledge.
- Score 0-6 : Poor knowledge

STATISTICAL METHODS

Data were organized, tabulated and analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. Version SPSS 18

RESULTS

Among 100 samples majority (32 %) of the subjects were 31-40 years old. In religious aspect 73% were Hindu and 26% were Muslim. As per gender 38% of samples were males and 62% were females. Majority samples (53%) have high school education and 21% have degree and above.

While considering the occupational status, 56 % of samples were homemakers, 23 % have private job, most of the subjects (42 %) had monthly family income below Rs1000, 68 % of subjects were members of nuclear family and 28 % subjects were joint family. In marital status 88% of samples were married and 12 % were unmarried. 33% of subjects have good knowledge on prevention of oral cancer while 64 % subjects have average knowledge on prevention of oral cancers. There is no significant association between age, gender, educational status, occupation, type of family, monthly family income and knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults.

Table 1 Level of knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults. (n=100)

Level of knowledge	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Good knowledge	33	33%	
Average knowledge	64	64%	12.23
Poor knowledge	3	3%	

Table 1 depicts that 33 % of samples have good knowledge, 64 % have average knowledge and 3% have poor knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer.

Table 2 Association between selected socio demographic variables and knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer. (n=100)

Variables	Chi square value	df	Table value
Age	0.0933	3	7.82
Gender	1.5266	1	3.84
Educational status	3.112	2	5.99
Occupation	1.844	3	7.82
Type of family	2.5	2	5.99
Monthly family income	5.282	3	7.82

The data given in table 2 depicts that there is no significant association between selected socio demographic variables and knowledge.

DISCUSSION

Findings from the present study showed that 33% of subjects have good knowledge, 64% of subjects have average knowledge and 3% of subjects have poor knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults. There was no significant association between selected socio demographic variables like age,

gender, educational status, occupation, type of family, monthly family income and knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults, but findings from study of XChenand L L Siu showed that mean knowledge score regarding knowledge on oral cancer was 4.60 ± 2.52 out of 17 and also there is association between race and education status. There was lower oral cancer knowledge among African Americans and those with low education. [1-5]

A large multi centric study was conducted by Alessandro et al to examine patients' knowledge regarding oral cancer risk factors and to explore communication and health messaging between clinicians and dental patients in Italy. The study findings showed that the majority (94 %) of individuals are knowledgeable regarding clinical signs associated with oral cancer (such as red/white patch and/ or mass/ulcer in the mouth). While knowledge of oral cancer was high overall, it did not appear that this information was being provided by clinicians: less than 15 % of participants reported receiving counseling about oral cancer from their physicians or dentists. [6,7]

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the present study 33 % of subjects have good knowledge, 64 % of subjects have average knowledge and 3 % of subjects have poor knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults and there is no

significant association between selected socio demographical variables like age, gender, educational status, occupation, type of family, monthly family income and knowledge regarding prevention of oral cancer among adults.

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